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Switching of research interest in careers and its impact on research performance – a gender perspective¹

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Introduction

How scientists choose and switch their research interests is of great significance not only for the development of science, but also for the scientists themselves. The topic has attracted considerable attention in studies in scientometrics, science of science, and sociology of science. The literature shows that it is widely accepted that switching of research interests during careers is linked with scientists' research performance and career development. As early as 1962, Kuhn (1962) argued that scientists who explore new fields will generate creative knowledge with profound impact. However, this risky strategy might also result in low productivity and even failure in the new fields. Recently, Yu et al. (2021) found empirical evidence that scientists with a larger change of research interest are more likely to produce papers with higher impact. In terms of productivity, Zeng et al. (2019) hold that a high switching probability in early career is associated with low overall productivity.

Despite these abundant investigations in research interests of scientists, few studies have explored this issue from the gender perspective. Zuckerman and Cole (1994) investigated whether systematic differences can be observed between men and women in the criteria of problem choice. However, this analysis was conducted with detailed qualitative interviews in early years and did not discuss impacts on research performance. In 2021, Zhang et al. (2021) found that differences in scientific and societal impact among males and females could be explained by gender differences in the aims of research projects.

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We find that the possible relation between changes in research interest during careers and research performance deserve further investigation. To what degree is the pattern dependent on gender? The tendency to shift interest might be different, and the effects of doing so might differ as well. To switch or not might lead to different research performance. Males and females might have different preferences in this choice. To cover such open questions, we summarize them in more specific research questions for this study:

RQ1: Are males more inclined to switch their research interests than females?

RQ2: Do males switch their research interests over wider distances than females?

RQ3: Do males benefit more from switching research interests than females in terms of research performance?

Our data covers a long-time span and allow for also looking at possible differences among generations of researchers.

We use a set of quantitative methods to check differences between gender, the switch of interest, and research performance. In RQ1 and RQ2, we compare the observed gender differences based on different indicators of interests switch. In particular, we propose a new measure to quantify the degree of switching research interests inspired by Jia et al. (2017). In RQ3, we investigate the indirect causal effect of gender in the relationship between switching research interests and research performance by using econometric models.

Scientists in Physics & Astronomy are selected as the case of this study for the following reasons: 1) The research interests are the main driving force of scientists in basic subjects. Therefore, it is suitable to investigate the switch of research interests of physicists; 2) As one of the disciplines with the largest gender gaps, gender issue in physics is a long-standing concern in academia (Strumia, 2021; Madsen et al., 2013; Eaton et al., 2020). Also, since many studies focus on gender imbalance in physics, it is more feasible to communicate and discuss our results with previous literature in the context of physics; 3) The subfields of physics are diverse and relatively clearly structured, which is favourable for distinguishing the research interests of scientists.

Due to the length limitation, we only include some of important findings in this submission. The complete results will be presented at STI 2022.

Data and methods

Dataset

The data of this study is obtained from Scopus (Elsevier). Each author ID in Scopus is identified as a scientist in our study. The author disambiguation of author ID is based on author name, affiliations, co-authors, subject areas, and publications. This method is verified reliable for large-scale analysis at the individual level by several studies (Moed et al., 2013; Kawashima & Tomizawa, 2015; Aman, 2017).

We used the article-level classification from Science-Metrix to identify research fields and subfields of papers. Journal-level classification is not adopted because articles published in a journal might belong to various subjects. Article-level classification is more sensitive to the change of research interests than journal-level one. The Science-Metrix classification is hierarchical and categorizes articles by six domains, 22 fields, and 176 subfields, with the subfields being mutually exclusive. In this classification, a scientific publication is attributed to a domain, field, and subfield based on its title, abstract, keywords, author affiliation, and citations, using a deep neural network. With this rich information, the method can operate even in the absence of reference or citation information, which makes up for the flaws of simple label

propagation approach, such as bibliographic coupling- and direct citation-based classifications. It is proven to be as precise as the simple label propagation approach above (Rivest et al., 2021).

To delimit our data, we first collected all scientists who have published at least one article in Physics & Astronomy according to Science-Metrix classification as the raw dataset. To eliminate authors that leave academia at an early stage of their career, we limit our analysis to scientists that (1) have authored at least one paper every three years; (2) have published at least ten papers in total; (3) have published papers for at least 20 years in Scopus. Afterward, we excluded scientists whose first article was published before 1960 because the data of Scopus in the early years is not comprehensive enough to confirm the preciseness of our study. Based on the criteria above, we obtained the dataset of scientists in Physics & Astronomy with integrated scientific careers. Then, we collected the publication data of these selected scientists. Only research articles in Physics & Astronomy are kept because we focus on the research interests within physics in this study. Scientists who switch to the fields beyond physics are not included.

We used the subfields to which articles belong to define and classify scientists' research interests. If a scientist publishes an article in a subfield that is different from the previous one, he/she is regarded to switch his/her research interest. Only scientists who have switched their research interests are included in our sample. To distinguish interdisciplinary collaboration from switching research interests, we selected only articles where these scientists are first authors or corresponding authors. After removing scientists who did not meet the criteria above, we arrived at 96,079 scientists and 1,680,951 articles in our dataset.

The authors' gender is inferred with a machine-learning-based classifier, Namsor, based on their first name, last name, and country. Considering the preciseness of the gender identity, we included only the authors whose gender inference for name and country exceeds 0.85 threshold, or the name-only inference exceeds 0.85 threshold. This algorithm has the limitation that it only provides a binary classification of gender. At last, we obtained 64,759 authors with satisfied gender inference (67.4% of the total sample), of which 58,563 are male and 6,196 are female.

Indicators and measurements

Based on the indicator presented in Jia et al. (2017), we modified it and proposed a new measure, *SwitchDegree*, to illustrate the dynamic and chronological changes of research interest over time. *SwitchDegree* quantifies the degree to which a scientist changes his/her research interest. For a given set of articles that a scientist published in a year (t), we generate a topic vector (s_t), the elements of which represent the occurrence of each research interest. Then, we use the complementary cosine similarity between two vectors based on adjacent years to quantify the annual interest change of a scientist. This annual *SwitchDegree* is used in the panel data to answer RQ3 about benefits from interest switch as:

$$\text{SwitchDegree} = 1 - \frac{s_t \cdot s_{t+1}}{\|s_t\| \cdot \|s_{t+1}\|}$$

To answer RQ2 about the distance of interest switch, for each scientist, we divided it by the total publication years to calculate the average frequency of change per year. A large *SwitchDegree* implies that the research interest of a scientist in current year is quite different from that in previous year.

In addition to *SwitchDegree*, we also calculate other indicators to portray the multidimensions of switching research interest, i.e. *Broadness*, *Diversity* etc. In this short paper, we only present results of *SwitchDegree* analysis.

To answer RQ3 about benefits from switching, we constructed two-way fixed effects panel data regression models to formally examine the relationship between switch of research interests and research performance. In this study, the research performance of a scientist is defined as the total productivity and mean FWCI of his/her outputs. We treat the productivity and citation impact of scientists as the dependent variables and *SwitchDegree* as the main explanatory variable. Gender is included as the interaction term. Gender equals 1 when the focal scientist is female, otherwise 0. Other variables that could influence scientists' productivity and citation impact are also included as the control variables (career length, the start year of switching interests, whether he/she return to the initial field or not, the generation).

Results

Gender difference in the magnitude of scientists who switch research interests

After selecting scientists who switched their research interests according to the criteria presented above, we obtained the results in Figure 1 (a). It illustrates that 9.57% of scientists who switched their research interests are females (N=6,196), which is lower than the share of all females in Physics & Astronomy (12.65%, N=19,231). It indicates that females are more inclined to have a constant research interest in general, while males are more likely to switch their research interests. The reason behind low representation of females can be complex. Indeed, females might be inclined to stay in the initial fields. However, females might also try to switch their research interests but fail to publish papers in a new field, which might lead to a survival bias. In addition, since the data collection is limited to physics, researchers who switch to fields beyond physics are not included in this study.

We divided our dataset into six groups according to scientists' start year of scientific career to observe the trend of interest switch for females (Figure 1 (b)). We found that the share of females who switched their research interests increased with generations. However, compared with the percentage of females in Physics & Astronomy, the growth rate of females who switch their research interests is lower than that of all females, especially for the recent generation. It reflects that the willingness and capacity of females to switch their research interests did not increase in the same degree with the growing representation of females in this field.

Figure 1: The number and proportion of scientists who switch research interests – gender comparisons.

Note: (a) “Switch” means the number of males and females who switch research interests. “Stable” means the number of males and females who remain stable research interest. “Total” represents all scientists in Physics & Astronomy. (b) “Total-switch” (blue) means total number

of scientists who switch research interests. “Female (%)–switch” (pink) denotes the proportion of females in the sample of scientists who switch research interests. “Female (%)–total” denotes the proportion of females in Physics & Astronomy. The X-axis represents the generations of scientists. The benchmark line is the proportion of females in the whole Physics & Astronomy.

Gender differences in SwitchDegree

We quantified the degree to which scientists switch their research interests with *SwitchDegree* and made comparisons of males and females in different generations (Figure 2). This indicator measures the average frequency of a scientist to switch his/her research interest per year. To make our results credible, we conducted the non-parametric tests of each group. Generally, the mean value of *SwitchDegree* of females is close to that of males in all groups before the 2000s. When considering generations, males' degree of research interest switch has become narrower over generation, while the *SwitchDegree* of female rebounded after 2000s. The gaps between males and females are widened and the gender differences became significant according to the p-value in the 2000s. It reflects the increasingly frequent change of females' research interests.

Figure 2: Gender differences in the average *SwitchDegree*.

Note: We conducted Mann Whitney U test between males and females. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$, ns $p > 0.1$

Gender disparity in the effect of switching research interests on research performance

With limited space, we refrain from presenting the specification of methodology and results of our benchmark models in the current version. However, we performed a series of grouped regressions that are visualized in Figure 3 with the coefficients of the main explanatory variables. In the following, gender is included as the interaction term to measure the moderating effect of gender in the relationship of switching research interests with research performance.

As shown in Figure 3 (a), we found that the *SwitchDegree* has a negative effect on the productivity of scientists. That is to say, the more widely a scientist switched his/her research interests, the fewer articles he/she would publish. Nevertheless, the estimated coefficients of

$SwitchDegree*gender^2$ are significantly positive from the 1970s, which is opposite to the main effect. It means that the negative effect of $SwitchDegree$ on productivity of scientists is weaker for females than males. This weakening effect also grows with generations. Similarly, in Figure 3 (b), the $SwitchDegree$ also has a negative effect on citation impact of scientists. When the scientist is female, this effect decreases in most groups of generation, except for the 1990s. However, the coefficients of the interaction term are not statistically significant and fluctuate in different group.

Figure 3: The effects of switching research interests on research performance and the moderating effects of gender.

Note: “ $SwitchDegree$ ” means the value of $SwitchDegree$ of scientist i in year t . The Y-axis reports coefficients estimated from regressions. The X-axis exhibits regression models grouped by generations of scientists. Each point represents an estimated coefficient. The colored area represents the 95% confidence intervals of the estimates. Panel (a) examines the total number of a scientist’ articles published in Physics & Astronomy. Panel (b) examines the mean FWCI a scientist received. If the interaction term ($SwitchDegree*gender$) and the main explanatory variable ($SwitchDegree$) are both negative or positive, the interaction term enhances the effect of the main explanatory variable, and vice versa³.

Conclusions and discussions

To conclude, this study showed that compared with female scientists, in general male scientists are more inclined to switch their research interest. Compared with the total share of females in Physics & Astronomy, the lower growth rate of females who switch research interests reflects their fading willingness for this risky strategy. Interestingly, from the sample of scientists who switch their research interests, we found that female scientists switch their research interests at wider distances than male scientists in recent years. By further investigation of the relationship with research performance, switching research interests was found to decrease the productivity and citation impact of a scientist. This result partly agrees with Zeng et al. (2019). Under this circumstance, females who choose to switch their research interests would have a smaller reduction in productivity compared with males.

The interpretation of our results is not straightforward, but we do hope our study may arouse useful discussions around researchers’ switches of interests, the related gender differences, and perhaps also gender disparities (Traag and Waltman, 2020) in STI 2022. It might be that scientists do not acquire higher citation impact or more publications from switching research interests, which makes switching to a new research field a risky strategy for scientists. Indeed, it takes time to grasp and accumulate knowledge from new fields. For female scientists, the

² Gender equals 1 when scientist i is female, otherwise 0.

³ For details about interaction terms, see Cortina, J. M. (1993). Interaction, Nonlinearity, and Multicollinearity: implications for Multiple Regression. *Journal of Management*, 19(4), 915–922.

“punishment” on citation impact is even greater. In addition, scientists, perhaps especially females, would face administrative and cultural barriers and sponsoring difficulties when they pursue risky strategies. Another obstacle might be that it is not easy to be recognized by peers from different fields, and this might be even harder for females. These facts could also partly explain the lower citation impact performance of females.

This study is still at the preliminary step of the continuing project. Considering the complexity of the research questions, in the current submission, we mainly compare the differences between males and females in switching research interests focusing on a generation perspective. In the next step, we will further analyse the dynamic gender differences along with the careers of scientists within a same generation.

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